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IT'S A NEW ADVENTURE WITH EVERY NEW STUDENT: A CRITIQUE OF THE DISSERTATION SUPERVISION PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

Starting with the question '*How do MSc Dissertation Supervisors view their role?*', this ongoing exploratory study focusing on supervisors' perceptions of their responsibility to develop students' study, professional, and analytical skills has been undertaken within a large engineering education department in the UK. An online survey was administered to a group of supervisors responsible for guiding graduate students through their full-time master's projects during the Covid-19 pandemic. The findings suggest that the majority of supervisors believe they have some responsibility for providing individual study skills support during the supervision process; although opinions differ with regards to the level of support that should be given. Changes to the supervision approach in response to Covid-19 are also identified and initial recommendations and suggestions for future research are shared.

1. INTRODUCTION

Set in a large engineering education department in a UK university, the research examines the question *‘How do MSc Dissertation Supervisors view their role?’*. This short paper uses descriptive data to review the perspectives of project supervisors on their supervisory role to develop the study, professional, and analytical skills needed by students to successfully complete a master’s level research project. This is significant since there is a lack of understanding about master’s supervision [1]. Yet successful supervision is a key factor for student’s achieving their degree and preparing for their career [2].

The master’s level research project is a key element of master’s study in the UK. Referring to the UK Quality Assurance Agency Characteristics Statement [3] for a Master’s Degree, it clearly states that:

“they are usually predominantly composed of structured learning opportunities (are ‘taught’). Frequently, at least a third of the course is devoted to a research project, leading to a dissertation /comparable research output or the production of other output such as an artefact, business plan, performance or musical composition” (p6).

It proceeds to clarify that:

“They include research methods training, which may be provided in a range of different ways (for example, through content modules)” (p6).

In the department there are slightly more than 1,200 full-time students from 15 diverse master’s courses who complete the dissertation. The dissertation is 90 credit points for most students, and equates to half of the marks awarded for the master’s degree. To support the students’ skills development to complete a research project, students can attend a year-long blended learning module that focuses on study, professional, and analytical skills. This module is not compulsory at present, but strongly encouraged, as it is important for preparing students for academic success. In addition, students have a project supervisor, an academic or industry professional, who provides mentorship throughout the independent research project.

This work was conducted as part of a more holistic review of the master’s project process and became increasingly relevant in light of the Covid-19 pandemic when support for students’ during their studies became disrupted due to cohorts being dispersed globally. This short paper analyses the survey responses of 89 project supervisors about their perceived supervisory responsibilities for students’ study, professional, and analytical skills development to complete the dissertation. Since this research is a work-in-progress, findings are not critiqued against literature as this will occur at a later stage. Initial recommendations and suggestions for further research are provided.

2. METHODOLOGY

To understand supervisors' expectations of their master's students' skills development and perceived responsibilities of supervision, a twenty question survey was sent to current supervisors during the Covid-19 pandemic in April 2020. The survey focused on four areas: students' skills development for the research project, the role of the supervisor, departmental processes, and impact of the first pandemic lockdown on supervision. An initial descriptive analysis of the data is presented here. Further development of the research will expand to include an analysis of supervisors' perceptions and practices for developing students' professional and analytical skills.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Supervisor Sample

A total of 89 professionals in academia and industry supervising master's students responded to the survey. Of the 89 participants, 38 were internal supervisors and 51 were external supervisors. The internal supervisors include members of the department or a different department within the university. External supervisors were divided into two groups: academic supervisors employed at a different HEI/FEI and 'others' that include supervisors that are employed in the business, industry, or public sector (excluding education), retired, or other. The sample breakdown is evidenced in Table 1. The study identified participants by supervisor position rather than other factors, such as gender or degree attainment, as the degree of closeness to the institution and higher education impact the extent of knowledge about available student support and expectations for student skills development. The multi-disciplinary portfolio of the master's programme is reflected in the diverse background of supervisors with experience in business and management, engineering, and social sciences.

Table 1. Breakdown of Sample Participants

Supervisor Position in University	<i>N</i>
Academic Supervisor (Internal – member of the department or university)	38
Academic Supervisor (External – employed at another HEI/FEI)	20
Other Supervisors (External)	31
Total	89

3.2 Supervisors' Perspectives of Students' Skills Development

A key finding is that a majority of academic supervisors, whether internal or external, perceive they have a minor to no responsibility to support their students' development of study skills, compared to other supervisors (external) who tend to perceive it as a major part of project supervision. This is evidenced in a cross tabulation in Table 2. It is also notable that more external academic supervisors see study skills support and

guidance as ‘something [they] should only do in exceptional circumstances’ or ‘not [their] role’ compared to the other groups.

Table 2. Cross tabulation of supervisors to perceived responsibility for providing ‘study skills’ support and guidance to individual students

“Providing study skills support and guidance to students is...” (% of responses per employment group)						
	<i>A major part of project supervision</i>	<i>A minor part of project supervision</i>	<i>Something that project supervisors should only do in exceptional circumstance</i>	<i>Not the project supervisor’s role</i>	<i>Not sure</i>	
Academic Supervisors (Internal)	38	56	-	6	-	100%
Academic Supervisors (External)	26	42	21	11	-	100%
Other Supervisors (External)	59	28	10	-	3	100%

It may be that supervisors who are currently employed in higher education are more likely to see the responsibility of the department to provide support through the study, professional, and analytical skills module rather than perceive supervision as a complementary process for reinforcing skills progress. In contrast, ‘other supervisors’ currently outside of higher education may not be as aware to the departmental or university support for students’ skills development.

More external academic supervisors (employed at a different HEI/FEI) perceived study skills support in exceptional circumstances or not part of their role may be due to their experience in their institution in which study skills and/or research methods training is credit-bearing and required. Hence external academic supervisors may have a different expectation on student skills development, particularly compared to internal supervisors, since the study, professional, and analytical skills module is unique compared to similar modules found in higher education institutions in that it is optional and not credit-bearing [4].

The difference between internal and external supervisors’ perceived responsibility for students’ skills development is also reflected in an open question asking supervisors to comment on the supervisory process. More external supervisors, typically those who are retired or are not employed at an HEI/FEI, recognised issues in students’ skills, such as academic writing or information literacy. Also they commented more frequently on students’ research competencies and/or the limitations of the non-

compulsory study, professional, and analytical skills module. For example, one colleague suggested:

“Some of this year’s [research methods] is unsuitable, causing students to switch off and game to get the exemplars so they can cut & paste because they do not understand.” (External Supervisor: Retired academic).

In contrast, internal supervisors tended to focus on the administrative processes that hinder or complicate supervision. For instance, one observed:

“[There is] too much dictate[d] by admin responsible for the management of the projects on supervisors” (Internal Supervisor: In the department).

A responsibility of supervision is to evaluate students’ academic skills and provide appropriate support and/or refer the student to a relevant service or resource for help [5]. Yet, in reflecting on the impact of Covid-19 in changing their approach to supervision, only 53% of supervisors signposted to the study, professional, and analytical skills module and encouraged their students to engage with it, and 31% of supervisors were ‘providing enhanced levels of one-to-one academic support’. A lack of academic skills signposting and individual support during the pandemic can be a consequence of supervisors’ changing workloads while adjusting to new working conditions in the pandemic. However, it is problematic as students’ skill levels vary by educational and cultural background, so students benefit from encouragement to engage in the study, professional, and analytical skills module to support their academic development. Also, students may be more successful when given individual support, such as personal attention for improving critical writing.

4. DISCUSSION

This work in progress begins to shine a light on the possibility that supervisors often have different perceptions of what their responsibility is with regards to supporting students’ study, professional and analytical skills development. Such inconsistencies in how supervisors view their role can lead to different levels of support being offered to different students on the same programme of study [6]. To resolve this matter the case-study organisation provides developmental opportunities and ongoing training for supervisors to ensure university processes are adhered to and colleagues are aware of their responsibilities. In addition to this, to promote consistency in the student experience, supervisors are encouraged to participate in internal and external peer networks to reflect upon and share good practice [7].

With such a large programme and with such a diverse range of supervisors, the challenge of ensuring a consistent level of expertise, approach and student experience

is not easy to address. Referring back to the QAA Characteristics Statement [3], the following clause reinforces the importance of ensuring the supervision process is effective and consistent:

“Graduates of research master’s are likely to be further characterised by their ability to study independently in the subject, and to use a range of techniques and research methods applicable to advanced scholarship in the subject” (p4).

Bearing this in mind and looking forward, there are plans underway to bring the study, professional, and analytical skills module within the wider accredited and credit-bearing programme; meaning that the module will become compulsory for all students. This will benefit supervision by allocating teaching time to students’ skills development and embedding within the curriculum the type of skills needed for students to succeed both in the taught and research components of their courses [8].

To adapt to the conditions of a global pandemic, supervision strategies that once worked required transformation to improve accessibility and utilise technology to enhance communication and feedback [9]. For example, signposting to study skills support during a once-a-month face-to-face meeting is impossible in a national lockdown. Instead, supervisors needed to increase their technology proficiency in order to forward emails or message their supervisees about upcoming developmental opportunities. Also, scheduling bimonthly meetings to increase the frequency of individual support to ensure students made progress on their project and received well-being support. Reflecting on strategies that supported students in their projects during Covid-19, such as new ways to record feedback, can help identify practices which enhance future supervision to the benefit of student learning and academic achievement. This is important as online supervision may need to continue given the variation of students’ circumstances that impact their ability to attend any pre-pandemic styles of face-to-face supervision.

CONCLUSION

This short paper presents an initial investigation into the supervision of master’s projects. Further research is needed to include the student perspective in regard to expectations of supervisors and perceived responsibility for skills development compared to the supervisors’ perspectives presented here. In addition, research into the impact of departmental processes and institutional culture on the supervision process will enable a greater understanding of master’s supervision.

In conclusion, project supervision represents a major part of colleagues’ professional time and commitments. Whilst training generally assures adherence to organisational policies and practice, there is a need for much more work to be done in this area.

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